

SUBSTANCE AND FUNCTION OF THE PARALOGY

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Annotation: Social behavior of man with all the diversity of specific historical conditions and place of the person in a society is caused, first of all by an opportunity communication of people with the help of language. Language as the direct embodiment of thinking materializes the process and result of man's cognitive activity and fixes in its form is any individual act of cognition as a social category. Verbal communication is in this sense a condition for the existence of man in a society that gives him the opportunity to develop material production as a basis all life.

Key Words: Language, material, person, individual, linguistic.

Language is by function a tool of communication, material and spiritual education, containing all the cognitive wealth of a person in an individual and the social aspect, fixing in a material form his individual and public consciousness. Proceeding from the fundamental definition of language, direct reality of thought, which is generally confirmed by the data of modern science in its various aspects (linguistics, psychology, physiology), it can be argued that the language is the only universal means of expressing the entire process of thinking rights. This premise gives grounds for talking about the absolute ability of the language express both the structure, the framework of thinking, and the filling of this framework by any conceptual content. Expressive resources of the language are made up of the sum of system and structural means at all levels of its material substance. Language is the primary natural expression of human thought. It should be said that language communication does not occur in a vacuum, and participants' communications are subject to the influence of all circumstances involved in the communication situation, whose awareness is to some extent contained in speech works. Just on against this background, the language reveals all its expressive possibilities. The process of verbal communication always occurs in some concrete situation, which contains many factors that are important for the content of the 6th communications. Thus, any dialogue, for example, is always "tied" to specific individuals with features of their voice, facial expressions, the context - the topic of conversation, etc. All these conditions transform the general scheme of communication and speech act with the participation of language factors, for example, assumptions with its

structure in interaction with all incidental factors, such as the mentally speaking state of the speaker, his manner of gesturing, the presence of unauthorized persons (which may be the reason for using "hints", etc.). Awareness of the need to include in one form or another in the linguistic research of factors directly accompanying speech, in modern Linguistics was clearly expressed in the "Theses of the Prague Circle" in which the concept of a functional approaches to language naturally required the expansion of the concept of "means of language communication".¹ In connection with this, these theses draw attention to the fact that "it follows systematically to the speaker at his direct communication with the listener, gestures relevant to the problem linguistic regional unions. "The theoretically conceivable possibility of communication, so to speak, in sterile conditions is associated with the creation of a purely logical language, where the unambiguous structure strictly determines the nature of information the independence of any conditions. (I.C. Brown, Loganudy the gestures accompanying and supplementing the verbal manifestations of a logical language: requirements for the logical language of Brown :) maximum availability; 2) neutrality; 3) simplicity; 4) completeness; 5) uniqueness. The study of the processes of verbal communication of information, therefore, should always rely on both linguistic and non-linguistic factors (or articulated and not articulated signs). Two pianas of language information, notes, for example, R. Dickson, namely the meaning internal and external and the first (internal) he refers to himself text, and the second (external) refers to the situation. To extract the actual values from the language structure. "Only the weight of a complex situation reveals to us the full and real meaning of the speech fragment," notes R. Dickson.² In the process of language development, the attendant circumstances in communicative process can be typed, and at the level of some generalization, these factors can be fixed in a specific area of language communication. These are knowledgeable for the language external, extra-linguistic factors consolidated their a certain speech type, as a result of which a symbiosis of intra and extra linguistic characteristics of the speech act. Despite the transitory nature of the external circumstances, there are some stereotypes of situations that accompany one type or another communication and defining this or that concrete content of the act of communication. The standard of speech situations arising on the basis of general laws communication, leads to the creation of a stable interaction of some speech samples with paralinguistic means specific for each specific language. Such an

¹ Theses of the Prague Circle" (Prague Linguistic circle, M., 1967, p. 25

² Dixon. R. What is language? London, 1965, ch.1

interaction includes, for example, the stereotype of an ellipse and an index test, question-answer and facial expressions, exclamatory sentence and features of voice and etc. In live speech communication, many circumstances accompanying the whole statement, and its fragments, and non-linguistic factors only accompany speech.

All non-linguistic factors play a supporting role in communication, the language plays main role, and it is always open for him to use for the message only own means. In this case, two phenomena that are not may indicate a somewhat different role of non-linguistic factors: 1) the language of the deaf, where the essence of gestures and symbols can be treated in two ways and as primary (actually language) system, and as a secondary (code - deputy); 2) sign language of some peoples, which can be regarded as a symbolic system of secondary origin, existing on the basis of natural language. Paralinguistic is a new linguistic discipline that deals with by studying the factors that accompany speech communication and participating in the transmission information (from the Greek couple - about). The prefix "par" is currently used for the designations of the branches of science dealing with related spheres and being auxiliary to the subject of research proper (for example, parapsychology). At the present time the name "paralinguistic" is firmly established in linguistics to denote the branch of science, engaged in the whole sphere of non-verbal communication. The paralinguistic aspect is of interest to linguistics only in combination with the study of verbal communication. The case of the so-called purely non-linguistic communication (for example, telepathy) Lie already outside the sphere of linguistics and paralinguistic, and is at the junction of psychology with physiological the process of combining the actual linguistic and non-lingual factors that accompany unequivocal transmission of communication, can be explained by two reasons: first, determined by the redundancy of the choice of verbal means, and secondly, the material concreteness of the communicative process. The nature of this peculiar, because it does not constitute an organic compound of intra- and extra linguistic factors, but is in its essence an amalgamation, lying on surface of the tongue. The extra linguistic factor cannot be included in the structure of the language, since the language system functions independently of external factors. In principle, the language the system itself is always sufficient, in order to express internally any mental content, including feelings, wills and various kinds of emotions. However, the possible redundancy of the language with full verbal disclosure of any or the content under natural conditions is removed for various reasons by elimination of purely linguistic

means. The removal of the redundancy of a speech utterance, dictated by certain goals communication, when verbal communication is virtually destroyed. It is in these paralinguistic means compensate for the missing minimum of the verbal structure of the utterance. When implementing a statement at the expense of its own structure of the language in the example *"Give me the book Anna Karenina"* by A.N. Tolstoy all other means are redundant. When folding of this phrase *"Give me that book"* indicating the bookcase communication is not destroyed, since here the gesture will suffice to compensate for the meaning of that book. When uttering only *"Give me"* not only removes any redundancy of the language, but eliminates and the very minimum that is necessary for understanding this phrase. To restore the information contained in this phrase, you must already have paralinguistic means as a compensating factor in the act of communication. It would generally be possible to distinguish two concepts: a) paralinguistics - as the science of not language proper. b) paralanguage - as the totality. However, in literature at the present time there is only the term "paralinguistic". Research work in this direction was carried out by historians of culture, philology, psychologists, anthropologists and other specialists. The range of issues discussed initially within paralinguistic, covering all kinds of kinesics (gestures, pantomimes), all kinds of phonation (speaking, vocal art) and all kinds of communication (situational context, dialogue). The scientific study of kinesics was initiated by Ch. Darwin, who fundamentally explored the question of the relationship between the origin of language and development gestures and facial expressions. Body movements involved in the transmission of information in the process of communication in the animal world and to its specific kind in human society to a large extent was explained by the search for universal regularities in any system of signs, considered in the semiotic sense includes the whole complex of kinetic phenomena and a number of other semantic markers. Functional understanding of the paralinguistic phenomena considered not in as an independent semiotic means, and the means accompanying the verbal transmission of information, presupposes a strict delineation of all sound, kinetic and other manifestations of human communicative behavior from those of them who are included in the complex of speech behavior and language communication.

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